

Figure 2. Guitar standard tuning used in the present study; The pitches of the open strings are displayed. Note that, in

Figure 6. A one-octave major scale starting from C4 (top) and the generated guitar tablature (bottom); The generated fingering fixes the index finger to the 5th fret to minimize the movement of the left hand thanks to the manually-set transition probabilities.

Figure 8. An excerpt from Frédéric Chopin’s “Fantasie in F minor, Op. 49” composed for pianos (top), the resulting arrangement for guitars (middle) and guitar tablature (bottom); The notes with red squares are omitted while the ones with red circles go up an octave in the resulting arrangement which is playable by guitars.

algorithm as the most probable sequence of hidden states. The piano score is not playable by guitars because it includes notes which are out of the pitch range of guitars (indicated with red circles) and notes that can not be stopped with four fingers (indicated with red squares). Such notes were modified through the automatic arrangement. The notes with red squares were omitted while the ones with red circles went up an octave. Among the notes with red circles, the second and third ones went up to overlap with existing notes and then they were omitted. After modifications explained above, we obtained the arranged version which is playable by guitars.

From the result, we see that automatic arrangement can be carried out using the same HMM for fingering determination with modified emission probability.

4. CONCLUDING REMARKS

We have introduced a framework based on HMM that solves fingering determination and arrangement in a unified way

